

Effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge and practice regarding breast self-examination among first Degree relatives of breast cancer patient visiting to oncology O.P.D. at selected hospitals

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ABSTRACT

Background: Breast cancer is the second most common cancer among people assigned female at birth in the United States. Each year, it's responsible for nearly 30% of all cancers among this demographic. The American Cancer Society estimates that there are about 287,850 new cases of invasive breast cancer and around 51,400 cases of ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS) annually among those assigned female at birth. The disease tends to be more prevalent among people who are middle-aged and older. The median age of diagnosis is 62

Materials and methods: A quasi experimental one group pre test post test design with evaluatory approach was undertaken in selected hospital. A total 60 first degree relative of breast cancer patient were selected by using non probability purposive sampling technique to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge and practice regarding breast self-examination among first degree relatives of breast cancer patient visiting to oncology O.P.D. at selected hospitals. A nurse investigator designed structured knowledge questionnaire and practice checklist to collect data. The data was analyzed by descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results: Study revealed that in pre-test level of knowledge majority of first Degree relatives of breast cancer patients had average knowledge (36), followed by poor knowledge (24), with none having good knowledge. In post-test majority (37), had good knowledge, followed by good and average knowledge (23), none of the relative had poor knowledge in post-test. Pre-test level of practice revealed that the majority of first degree relatives of breast cancer patients had fair practice (33 relatives), followed by poor practice (27 relatives), and none of relatives had good practice, post-test level of practice revealed that the majority of first degree relatives of breast cancer patients had favorable practice (40), followed 20 relatives with good practice and none of relatives had poor practice in post-test.

Conclusion: The study concluded that the structured teaching program was effective in improving the knowledge and practice regarding breast self examination among first degree relative of breast cancer patient visiting Oncology OPD of selected hospital.

INTRODUCTION

What is Breast Cancer?

Breast cancer is a disease that arises when cells in one or both breasts grow uncontrollably. As these cells divide more rapidly than they should, they can accumulate into a tumor.

Breast cancer can begin in any of the three main parts of the breast:

- The lobules (glands that produce milk)**
- The ducts (tubes that transport milk to the nipple)**
- The connective tissue that surrounds them**

According to the World Health Organization, about 85% of breast cancers start in the cells lining the ducts and 15% begin in the cells lining the lobules.³ At stage 0, the beginning of breast cancer, the disease is usually symptomless and contained within the lobule or duct. Breast cancer may then invade nearby breast tissue, lymph nodes, and then other organs. This spreading, or metastasis, can make breast cancer fatal.

When breast cancer is diagnosed early, treatment options like surgery, radiation, chemotherapy, and hormonal therapy can help reduce the risk of death.¹

Signs and symptoms of breast cancer may include:

- A breast lump or thickened area of skin that feels different from the surrounding tissue.**
- A nipple that looks flattened or turns inward.**
- Changes in the color of the breast skin. In people with white skin, the breast skin may look pink or red. In people with brown and Black skin, the breast skin may look darker than the other skin on the chest or it may look red or purple.**
- Change in the size, shape or appearance of a breast.**
- Changes to the skin over the breast, such as skin that looks dimpled or looks like an orange peel.**
- Peeling, scaling, crusting or flaking of the skin on the breast.²**

Causes

The exact cause of most breast cancers isn't known. Researchers have found things that increase the risk of breast cancer. These include hormones, lifestyle choices and things in the environment. But it's not clear why some people who don't have any factors get cancer, yet others with risk factors never do. It's likely that breast cancer happens through a complex interaction of your genetic makeup and the world around you. Healthcare professionals know ¹²

that breast cancer starts when something changes the DNA inside cells in the breast tissue. A cell's DNA holds the instructions that tell a cell what to do. In healthy cells, the DNA gives instructions to grow and multiply at a set rate. The instructions tell the cells to die at a set time. In cancer cells, the DNA changes give different instructions. The changes tell the cancer cells to make many more cells quickly. Cancer cells can keep living when healthy cells would die. This causes too many cells. The cancer cells might form a mass called a tumor. The tumor can grow to invade and destroy healthy body tissue. In time, cancer cells can break away and spread to other parts of the body. When cancer spreads, it's called metastatic cancer. The DNA changes that lead to breast cancer most often happen in the cells that line the milk ducts. These ducts are tubes designed to carry milk to the nipple. Breast cancer that starts in the ducts is called invasive ductal carcinoma. Breast cancer also can start in cells in the milk glands. These glands, called lobules, are designed to make breast milk. Cancer that happens in the lobules is called invasive lobular carcinoma. Other cells in the breast can become cancer cells, though this isn't common.²

Prevalence of Breast Cancer

Breast cancer is the second most common cancer among people assigned female at birth in the United States. Each year, it's responsible for nearly 30% of all cancers among this demographic. The American Cancer Society estimates that there are about 287,850 new cases of invasive breast cancer and around 51,400 cases of ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS) annually among those assigned female at birth. The disease tends to be more prevalent among people who are middle-aged and older. The median age of diagnosis is 62.

Tragically, breast cancer is a leading cause of cancer death among people assigned female at birth, killing approximately 43,250 each year. Overall, the incidence of breast cancers has grown by .5% per year in recent years. However, the death rate has declined: 43% through 2020. Experts attribute this change to early detection, awareness campaigns, and treatment improvements. Now, there are more than 3.8 million breast cancer survivors in the United States.¹

Breast Cancer Prevention

Exercising regularly, maintaining a healthy weight, moderating alcohol consumption, and breastfeeding your children, if possible, are some ways to reduce the risk of breast cancer.

Having risk factors does not mean that breast cancer will develop. Some people with several risk factors never develop breast cancer, while others with no known risk factors get the disease. Discussing one's individual health with a healthcare provider can help with understanding personal risks.¹ 13

Breast Cancer Types

Most breast cancers begin in the cells lining the milk ducts or lobules. There are other types of cancer that can be found in the breast, but they are rare. This includes:

- **Sarcomas, which can begin in the connective breast tissue cells. Sarcomas account for less than 1% of breast cancers.**
- **Angiosarcomas, which begin in cells that line blood vessels or lymph vessels and can involve breast tissue or skin.**
- **Paget's disease of the breast, which starts in the breast ducts and spreads to the skin of the nipple (accounting for 1% to 3% of breast cancers).**
- **Phyllodes tumor of the breast, which is usually a benign growth in the connective tissue of the breast. It can sometimes be cancerous. Phyllodes tumors of the breast are rare.¹**

Problem Statement

“Effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge and practice regarding breast self-examination among first Degree relatives of breast cancer patient visiting to oncology O.P.D. at selected hospitals.”

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess knowledge and practice about breast self-examination among first degree relation of breast cancer.
2. To determine the effectiveness of structured teaching program on Knowledge and Practices among first degree relation of breast cancer patient.
3. Find out the association between knowledge and practices regarding Breast self-examination among first degree relation of breast cancer patient with their demographic variable.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and methods: A quasi experimental one group pre test post test design with evaluatory approach was undertaken in selected hospital. A total 60 first degree relative of breast cancer patient were selected by using non probability purposive sampling technique to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge and practice regarding breast self-examination among first degree relatives of breast cancer patient visiting to oncology O.P.D. at selected hospitals. A nurse investigator designed structured knowledge questionnaire and practice checklist to collect data. The data was analyzed by descriptive and inferential statistics.

Hypotheses

H01- There will be no significant difference between mean pre-test & post-test knowledge score of experiment group.

H1- There will be significant difference between mean pre-test & post-test knowledge score of experiment group.

H02- There will be no significant association between pre-test knowledge score of experiment group and control group with selected demographic variables.

H2- There will be significant association between pre-test knowledge score of experiment group and control group with selected demographic variables.

RESULTS

The results of the study have been organized according to the objectives of the study.

1. To assess knowledge and practice about breast self-examination among first degree relation of breast cancer. Pre test knowledge revealed that the majority of first Degree relatives of breast cancer patients have Average knowledge (36), followed by poor knowledge (24), with none having good knowledge in pre test. Where as in post test knowledge revealed that the majority (37), were have good knowledge among first Degree relatives of breast cancer patients followed by have Good and average knowledge (23), none relative have Poor knowledge in post test.

Pre test level of practice revealed that the majority of first Degree relatives of breast cancer patients have fair practice (33 relatives), followed by poor practice (27 relatives), and none of relatives having good practice in pre test. While in post test level of practice revealed that the majority of first Degree relatives of breast cancer patients have favorable practice (40), followed 20 relatives have good practice and none of relatives have poor practice in post test.

2. To determine the effectiveness of structured teaching program on Knowledge and Practices among first degree relation of breast cancer patient.

Effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding breast self Examination, in pre-test having a mean of 11.13, standard deviation of 3.13, and 37.11% mean, while the post-test has a mean of 19.65, standard deviation of 2.28, and 35.5% mean, with a paired t-test value of 23.397 and p-value of 0.000 and it is significant knowledge gain after intervention at the level of 0.05. This indicates a significant improvement from the pre-test to the post-test, as evidenced by the paired t-test result (0.001), which is less than the typical significance level of 0.05. Hence stated hypothesis Ho1 is rejected and H1 is accepted.

Effectiveness of structured teaching program on practice regarding breast selfexamination, in pre-test having a mean of 26, standard deviation of 5.24, and 52% mean, while the post-test has a mean of 34.37, standard deviation of 3.92, and 68.73% mean, with a paired t-test value of 11.547 and p-value of 0.000 and it is significant practice gain after intervention at the level of 0.05. This indicates a significant improvement from the pre-test to the post-test, as evidenced by the paired t-test result (0.001), which is less than the typical significance level of 0.05. Hence stated hypothesis Ho1 is rejected and H2 is accepted.

Priya, Padma. (2024). A similar study was conducted to assess Effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on self-breast examination among women. 100 samples who fulfilled the inclusion criteria was selected, using non probability purposive sampling technique. The pretest level of existing knowledge was assessed using a selfstructured questionnaire consisted of 25 questions. In phase II, the women who completed pretest were given video assisted teaching program on breast self-examination using video which lasted for about 20minutes which included the signs and symptoms and steps of breast self-examination. In phase III, a post test was conducted after 7 days from the day of video assisted teaching program with the same self-structured questionnaire which was given in pretest. This table shows the frequency and percentage distribution of level of knowledge on breast self-examination among women. The pretest data illustrated that 90 (90%) of them had inadequate knowledge, 10 (10%) of them had moderate knowledge and none of them had adequate knowledge in post-test of women 88 (88%) had adequate knowledge, 12 (12%) had moderate knowledge and none of them had inadequate knowledge. Thus, the study concluded that video assisted teaching program has an effect on improving the knowledge on breast self-examination among women.

3. To find out the association between knowledge and practices regarding Breast self-examination among first degree relation of breast cancer patient with their demographic variable.

Association between pre test level of knowledge with Age of participants., Relation to the patient , Religion., Area of living., Type of family., Family income per month., Is their history of breast cancer?, Have you attended any educational program regarding breast self examination?, the chi square p value found to be 0.941, 0.752, 0.992, 0.525, 0.593, 0.341, 0.576, and 0.490 respectively and it is no significant the level of 0.05. Hence stated hypothesis Ho2 is rejected and H3 is accepted.

Association between pre test level of practice with Age of participants., Relation to the patient , Religion., Area of living., Type of family., Family income per month., Is their history of breast cancer?, Have you attended any educational program regarding self breast examination?, the chi square p value found to be 0.649, 0.497, 0.081, 0.938, 0.357, 0.362, 0.271, and 0.610 respectively and it is no significant the level of 0.05. Hence stated hypothesis Ho2 is accepted and H3 is rejected.

DISCUSSION

This chapter deals with the finding of the present study, “Effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge and practice regarding breast self-examination among first Degree relatives of breast cancer patient visiting to oncology O.P.D. at selected hospitals” In this chapter an attempt has been made to discuss the findings of the study in accordance with objective of the study. Descriptive study was utilized to accomplish the objectives of the study. 60 first Degree relatives of breast cancer patient were selected for the study. The setting for the area was PNC ward in selected hospitals. Non-Probability convenient sampling technique was used to select the sample from selected PNC ward. The tool consists of demographic data and structured knowledge questionnaire on knowledge and practice check list regarding Breast self-examination among first Degree relatives of breast cancer patient. and tool was administered to collect the data from the first-degree relatives of breast cancer patient. The data was collected and analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of the present study indicated Effect of Structured Teaching Programme on Knowledge and Practice regarding Breast self-examination among the First degree relatives of breast cancer patient . This notable increase knowledge and practice is supported by the paired t-test result of 23.397 and 11.47 with a p-value of 0.000, and 0.001 respectively indicating that the difference between the pre-test and post-test scores is statistically significant. Thus, the results suggest a marked improvement in knowledge and practice after the intervention.

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